

Metaphysical Dimensions of *Arabesque* by Germaine Dulac in the Context of *Black Square* by Kazimir Malevich

In this chapter I follow the visual similarities between abstract images in *Arabesque* by Dulac and Suprematist paintings by Malevich. In doing so, I try to find out if the meaning of the first ones can go beyond psychological and social meanings usually attributed to them and enter the sphere of metaphysical issues. To answer this question, I examine the role of light and Dulac's method of using it in abstract images. In 'Background, Inspirations, Early Work' I briefly present her life, art circles she was involved with, and influences which inspired her work. I define the main sources of her creative impulses and crucial points of interests, stressing the specific use of light, whose power of expression she discovered in Symbolist theatre and Pre-Raphaelite paintings. This is illustrated with the examples of films in which she uses light to render emotions, reveal the inner world of the protagonists and create the ambient of her works. In 'Motif of Light' I start with her earliest works, where one can already notice a tendency to use light for abstracting the image. Her ultimate turn towards pure cinema in 1929 brings the change of optics from figurative to abstract. I argue that it is not rhythm, as usually suggested, but a specific use of light which plays a crucial role in this shift. In '*Arabesque, Black Square and Table*', a piece of poetic text helps me to look at the three different images: *Black Square* (1915) by Malevich, *Arabesque* (1929) by Dulac and my own film *Table* (2015), dwelling on subtle relations between these artworks and setting up a common ground for reflection. What comes to the fore in these pieces is the role of light in changing an object into a "figure". Dulac's method of abstracting objects understood as means of "translating certain ideas" (Williams, 2007a, p. 94) is contrasted then with the idea of freeing an object from the indexical bonds, which happens in Malevich's *Black Square*

(Bulgakova, 2002). This strategy lets me examine if abstract images in *Arabesque* transcend the previous indexical attachments. The section 'Light and Matter' concentrates on the analytical character of Dulac's works. To understand this issue, abstract images from her film are placed against a broader intellectual background of the epoch. I analyse the idea of the identity of image and movement (Bergson, *Matter and Memory*, 1896), and Einstein's equation between light and matter developed around that time and later adopted to the reflection on cinema (Bergson, *Duration and Simultaneity*, 1922; Deleuze, *Cinema 1*, 1983). The idea of the ontological unity of these elements, when applied to the Dulac's images, stresses their metaphysical character.

Literature Review

The discourse developed around the French pure cinema of the 1920s and 1930s was set, on the one hand, against other traditional performative temporal arts like theatre, opera and ballet, on the other – against Symbolist aesthetics, significantly influencing the creative environment of those days. The idea of synaesthesia came very strongly to the fore, bringing musical language to film criticism. Dulac's *Arabesque*, which I decided to take as a context for one of my studio works, being one of many films of those days structured around musical motifs,¹ has been prevalently commented on from the perspective of film as visual music. The language of critical reflection on film of that epoch was, and still is, dominated by notions from the writing on opera and ballet. Words like rhythm, movement, symphony, describing films keep coming back alongside the notions of life, truth, sincerity and beauty. To give just a few examples: Louis Delluc's description of Cecil B. DeMille's *Joan the Woman* seems to be more appropriate for a light-and-music performance than for a narrative film: "Everything is alive and lives according to an imposed rhythm. Just as in a symphony each note contributes its own vitality to the general line, each shot, each shadow moves, disintegrates or is reconstituted according to the requirements of a powerful orchestration" (McCreary, 1976, pp. 22-23). Émile Vuillermoz similarly commented *Le Coupable* (1917) by André Antoine, which he "described as a symphony . . . in which the images 'of the great, grim maternal city' of Paris created an accompaniment of 'deep and moving bass chords' to

¹ E.g. *La Dixième Symphonie* by Abel Gance, see McCreary, 1976, p. 22.

the ‘brave, noble melody’ of the drama” (Abel, 1985, p. 24). However, what drew my attention to *Arabesque* by Dulac was not the musical issues but the process of abstracting figurative images by the specific use of light and their similarity to Malevich’s Suprematist paintings. To understand the possible relation between Suprematist painterly work and Dulac’s pure cinema, I needed to delve deep into the understanding of light in the works of both of these artists. However, the subject of light in avant-garde films is rarely explored, and when it is mentioned, it refers back to the rhythm. To give an example: David Bordwell mentions Riccioto Canudo’s claim that the film “captures the rhythm of light” (1980, p. 99), according to Elie Faure it “unrolls in a musical space” (ibid. p. 100), while “Gance announces . . . that rhythm makes cinema the music of light” (ibid. p. 124). Bordwell himself gives the most all-encompassing outlook on the theory of Impressionist cinema and the importance of rhythm: “Impressionist theory rests its idea of filmic construction almost wholly upon the rhythmic relationships between images” (ibid.).

To my knowledge, Dulac’s work has never been interpreted exclusively in these categories. Many records of the artist’s inspirations stress a strong influence of Symbolism and this served as a point of departure for my research on light in her work. Tami Williams’ in-depth study on Dulac’s life and work (2007a, 2014) served as a source of information for my understanding of critical writing developed around her filmography in the 1920s and 1930s, although this eminent critic and expert on Dulac did not analyse the artist’s non-narrative work from the perspective of light. Speaking about Dulac’s narrative films, Williams (2014) remarks that her use of light to express human emotions, spirituality and sublimity is rooted in the theatrical *mise-en-scène*² and Symbolic inspirations. Importantly, Williams also briefly mentions Dulac’s encounter with sacred Medieval paintings, in which “beauty and divinity merge” through the use of light (p. 14); reputedly, this fact had a bearing on Dulac’s future work.

Interestingly, Myroslava M. Mudrak in the essay *Kazimir Malevich, Symbolism and Ecclesiastic Orthodoxy* (2017) mentions Malevich’s inspirations not only with the Russian icon but also with Symbolism, particularly with its French version. The discovery of Malevich’s and Dulac’s intersecting fascinations helped me to find the background against

² I write about it in more detail in the Chapter below.

which I could place these two artists. As I have already mentioned, I did not come across any critical writing which directly analysed abstract imagery in Dulac's work. Jurg Stenz (2014) mentions vaguely that "In recent years the significance of the four music-related films she [Dulac] made in 1928–1929 – a sort of counterweight to Germany's 'absoluter Film' – has . . . been recognized" (p. 221), but he does not provide any details. Considering his interests, I have reasons to believe that this remark does not concern the similarity of abstract imagery occurring in absolute cinema and *Arabesque* but its musical layer. For my comparison of her works with Hans Richter's *Rhythm21* and *Black Square* by Malevich I relied on Esther Leslie's *Hollywood Flatlands: Animation, Critical Theory and the Avant-Garde*, in which the author looks into how void in the form of a white and a black screen was adopted to painterly and filmic images by the first avant-garde. The process of abstracting a figurative image, essential for achieving the shadow-and-light pictures in *Arabesque*, is analogous to Malevich's approach to the process of liberating images from attached signification, which was explained by Olga Bulgakova (2002) in her essay *Malevich in the Movies*. The over-exposure used by Dulac inspired me to search for the possible understanding of her abstract images in the ideas of the relationship between light and matter, which emerged at the beginning of the twentieth century and which influenced strongly thinking on cinema. Bergson's two seminal works turned out to be crucial for my reflection: *Matter and Memory* (1896) and *Duration and Simultaneity* (1922). Together with their revival through Deleuze's *Cinema1: The Movement Image* (1983) they helped me to argue for the importance of light in creating the metaphysical character of *Arabesque*.

Background, Inspirations, Early Works

Germaine Dulac started her artistic career in France after WW1, quickly becoming one of the most recognisable figures in French avant-garde circles, not only as a director of silent films, but also as a theatre and film critic, journalist, film producer, a head of the French Film Club Federation, and a leading member of the Committee against Film Censorship (Stenzl, 2014, p. 221). In effect of her various activities, she was one of the most influential figures in the French film culture of the time. However, her greatest impact on the artistic and intellectual

milieu of the first avant-garde was through her film works. Her ability to show psychological states of characters has been frequently commented on. In this sense Dulac's films can be seen as part of the so called French school, which, in the opinion of Deleuze, is associated with the phenomenon of spirituality and sublimity expressed through such cinematic techniques as lighting and superimpositions.³ And yet, Dulac's work was strongly indebted to the theatre, namely, her use of light, mise-en-scène, as well as thematic and stylistic choices and a "remarkably modern style of acting" (Williams, 2007a, p. 53) can be traced back to her involvement with such important figures of the stage as Aurélien Lugné-Poe and Suzanne Despres.⁴ Spirituality and sublimity, frequently attributed in her films to movement and rhythm, are regarded as the artist's inspiration with not only Symbolist theatre but also contemporary ballet. This is also true of her narrative and abstract films. According to Tami Williams (2007b, p. 125), "while in her narrative films Dulac often expresses emotional and spiritual states of her characters through the movement and symbolism of dance, it is in her . . . experimental films (1929) that dance took on its full significance on a formal level".

Motif of Light

The issue of light occasionally emerges in the critical writing on Dulac's films, yet its role has never been analysed in depth. Commentary evolving around *The Smiling Madame Beudet* (1923) can serve as an example. Williams mentions the use of light for producing a specific mood and expressing psychological states of the protagonist, but she disregards the role of light in the artist's later, integral (other words, pure) cinema work:

Dulac evokes Madeleine's melancholy by following these shots [M. playing the piano] with images of nature, light and water . . . these images associated with Debussy's composition can be seen to correspond to Madeleine's inner world, as

³ Deleuze in his *Cinema 1* mentions that the same cinematic techniques, e.g. superimposition, were used in the French school to give expression to the soul, while in Vertov's films they served to express a materialist perspective. "[W]ith the French these [montage techniques] show primarily a spiritual power of the cinema, a spiritual aspect of the 'shot'. It is through the spirit that man goes beyond the limits of perception . . . Vertov's use of these procedures [on the other hand] was to express the interaction of distant material points" (Deleuze, 1986, p. 84). Deleuze mentions Gance, Herbiere and Epstein as the representatives of the French school, but considering her work and background, it is evident that Dulac also belongs to this group.

⁴ T.M. Williams mentions that "Dulac's contact in 1907 with the stage actress Suzanne Despres and her husband, avant-garde director, principal creator and the promoter of the French Symbolist theatre, Aurélien Lugné-Poe (1869-1940), greatly impacted her cinematic approach, and particularly her thematic and stylistic choices" (Williams, 2007a, p. 53).

well as the space of her imagined liberty. This sequence also anticipates Dulac's conception of a pure or integral cinema based exclusively on life, movement and rhythm . . . (Williams, 2007a, p. 194).

Although Dulac repeatedly experiments with light, making it an important means of expression, predominant comments concentrate on the use of light in connection with her narrative work,⁵ without seeing it as a leading element in her evolution from narrative to pure cinema. However, although this issue does not occupy any significant place in critical writing, its importance for Dulac's later turn towards pure cinema can be noticed even in her earliest films. Thus, in 1915 the artist produced *Les Soeurs Ennemies*, in which she deliberately used the power of light to create the ambient of the shots. Williams mentions that

Dulac . . . employed numerous techniques . . . to create psychological effect. For example, in the first scene of Les Soeurs Ennemies, she used the light and shadow cast by a mobile lamp in order to express the worry of the older sister . . . Later in the film, she used the light and shadow of a lamp and a gas stove . . . to show Lucille's evolving psychological state (Williams, 2007a, pp. 93-94).

Although the understanding of light as a conveyer of emotions – a lesson learned from her theatrical experience – found its expression in *Les Soeurs Ennemies*, this was not Dulac's ultimate goal. The exploration of cinematic possibilities in creating abstract images and the development of her work leading towards it can be spotted already in her next film, *Âmes de fous*. Created in 1918, it was "mildly criticised" (Williams, A., 1992, p. 146) for the overuse of back lighting, which reduced actors to dark silhouettes. From the wider perspective of her works, however, it was not a mistake but a first step towards the images of pure cinema. For Dulac, this film was an attempt to explore the potential of light as one of cinematic image-building elements. She wrote: "Lighting, camera position and editing seemed . . . more important than the simple workings of a scene played in accordance with the laws of the stage" (ibid.), thus, acknowledging the importance of light in the process of the evolution towards artists' (pure) cinema. The unique ability of the cinematic image to create abstract images without losing connection with the known world has been noticed by the filmmakers and critics alike. This could be achieved by the specific filmic means, like lighting

⁵ See 'Literature Review'.

among others, and could open up an enormous richness of the possibilities of expression. Louis Delluc, who was not only a film theoretician and a film director but also Dulac's friend and scriptwriter for one of her films, wrote: "All could be made to speak in a film: an object, a landscape, the quality of light (McCreary, 1976, p. 17). Mc Creary develops his idea: "For 'the secret of the inexhaustible in expression' is never completely saying everything. Rhythm and light were not thought, but they incited to thought" (ibid. p. 20). Delluc was not alone in this conviction but rather expressed a popular belief. Virginia Woolf in her essay *The Cinema* written in 1920, published for the first time in 1926 in *The Nation and Athenaeum*, gives a similar commentary. She accentuates the possibility of cinematic image to create ambiguity through abstract or semi-abstract symbols: "Something abstract, something which moves with controlled and conscious art, something which calls for the very slightest help from words or music to make itself intelligible, yet justly uses them subserviently—of such movements and abstractions the films may in time to come be composed. Then indeed when some new symbol for expressing thought is found, the film-maker has enormous riches at his command" (Woolf, 2007, p.843).

In 1927 Dulac began using her previous experiments with the cinematic image to create non-narrative films. This new approach was based on her conviction that "the lines and forms of gesture and figuration, central to . . . narrative films could move the spectator without actors and characters" (Williams, 2007b, p. 125). Thus she produced three filmic works inspired by music: *Arabesque*,⁶ *Disque 957* (1929) and *Themes and Variations* (1929).⁷ In *Arabesque* images are endowed with various degrees of abstraction, yet at the same time they differ significantly from the abstract works of so-called absolute cinema created at about that time in Germany.⁸ Although absolute cinema was also often inspired by music (e.g. *Diagonal Symphony* (1924) by Viking Eggeling), it was based on frame-by-frame animation and was fully controlled by the artist, while *Arabesque* is a result of Dulac's discerning observation of nature, which puts them close to the Woolf's vision. Williams claims that this difference springs from the fact that for filmmakers like Eggeling or Hans Richter "a non-figurative and

⁶ Dulac's film was inspired by *Two Arabesques* by Debussy (Meeker and Szabari, 2020).

⁷ Although some sources give 1928 as the date of the production of the two latter films, I am following the dating provided by Tami Williams (2007a).

⁸ "Unlike the surprise of fragments and montage in the avant-garde cinema of Richter, Eggeling, Leger or Clair, Dulac's abstraction is created by rhythms that unite art and life, an abstraction that moves the viewer" (Andrew, 2020, p. 142)..

non-referential approach derives from painting [while] for Dulac, cinégraphie remained present in . . . the visualisation of movement and rhythm” (Williams, 2007b, p. 125). Nell Andrew’s commentary resonates with the above: “Her [Dulac’s] abstraction . . . is importantly born not from a will to form but from a will to enact . . . This link between gesture, movement, and rhythm will be central in her move towards abstraction as a means of social expression” (Andrew, 2020, p. 142).⁹

Andrew expounds the view (which agrees with the opinion of a number of critics) that it is the employment of specific movement which allows the transformation of the optics in Dulac’s work from figurative to abstract:

Despite their [serpentine films] varying levels of formal abstraction or representational imagery, they are united in conveying abstraction through a sense of movement without beginning or end, that is in continuous gestures designed to stimulate the precognitive sensorium . . . real bodies, objects and images become abstract by negating their availability to be fixed, formed or captioned. . . (ibid. p. 145).¹⁰

In *Arabesque*, however, if we were to separate abstract images and look at them as stills, we could notice that what links otherwise completely abstract images with the system of signification attached to the initial, figurative picture, is movement. Yet, the element which allowed the shift from the figurative to the abstract optics is not so much movement (mentioned above by Andrew), as light.

Arabesque, Black Square and Table

In this text I compare a few images from *Arabesque* with my work *Table* and with *Black Square* by Malevich. In the first paragraph I reflect on the objects in *Arabesque* losing their details because of overexposure. (While reading I would suggest to watch *Arabesque*, 0:13-0:29 min.) My reflection is accompanied by a quote from Malevich’s *Non-objective World*

⁹ Importantly, next to “gesture, movement and rhythm” – elements which are repeatedly analysed, Andrew mentions the social and feminist dimension of Dulac’s pure cinema work: “Addressing this topic [the place of a woman in the society after WW1] from outside the gendered hegemony at the moment of high national spirit, Dulac began to lean on modes of abstraction to make room for alternative realities and interpretations” (ibid.). Such social reading of her abstract works can be found also among other critics, e.g. Williams (2007b), Dozoretz (1982).

¹⁰ Andrew (2020, p. 142) goes on: “Dulac’s idea of integral cinema is found in the abstract in-between where the self and the world are synthesized through feeling”.

(1927). The quote, originally referring to *Black Square*, proves that the idea of non-objectivity can be also applied to the images in *Arabesque*. The second and the third paragraphs develop the idea that vision can happen only within specific, narrow section within the strength of light. Here I concentrate on the borderline between vision and non-visibility, the place which although brings objects to vision, renders them unrecognizable, deprived of detail, detached from the system of signification. The second paragraph bridges *Arabesque* and *Table*, while the third one refers to *Table*. (I would recommend watching *Table* at this point.) The next paragraph is devoted to another image from Dulac's work (see *Arabesque* 0:30 – 0:32 min.), which shows even stronger visual kinship with *Black Square*, being almost its negative. Another quote from Malevich (referring to *Black Square*) stresses the relevance of the Suprematist ideas to *Arabesque's* images. The purpose of this text is to change the perspective on *Arabesque* by, firstly: to stress the role of light in the process of rendering images abstract, secondly: to reveal their relation to Suprematist ideas.

Arabesque (0:13 – 0:29)

*Black arcs of lines placed against the sky.*¹¹ *Thicker branches interweaving with a net of thinner ones. Scarce leaves still holding to them show it is wintertime. They move rhythmically against the background of soft shapes of floating clouds. The image changes suddenly and without any warning as if taken by surprise by yet another image. The edges of the frame get stained with mysterious black dye. From them, a chaotic net of thicker and thinner lines spreads in all directions. The closer to the source of light, the fainter they seem. Light dematerialised parts of the net, rendering some of the lines barely perceptible. What are these shapes? Are they a maze of roots, or veins conveying blood, a microscopic image of neurons or a watercolour pigment spreading chaotically in a puddle of a liquid? A sudden flash of blinding glow spreading concentrically burns out a hole in the middle of the net, engulfing fragile shapes located close to it. The bush in the desert does not burn up, though it is on fire. The bush consumed by fire comes back to existence, being – through the power of light – in a constant state of transcending its own ontological status from being an object to*

¹¹ To analyse how light is used to build images in *Arabesque*, I examined the shots in which an overly strong contrast between light and shadow deprived the image of details and rendered it abstract.

being pure energy. “No more ‘likeness of reality’, no idealistic images – nothing but a desert! But this desert is filled with the spirit of non-objective sensation which pervades everything” (Malevich, 2003, p. 68).¹² But this abstract image comes back to the world of objective associations.

Fig. 5 G. Dulac, *Arabesque*¹³ (1929)

Thanks to the gentle trembling motion we can see the convoluted pattern of lines and spots as branches moved by the breeze.

Table <https://vimeo.com/456888106>

A piece of a shabby white board with lumps of soil adhering to it, burn marks, scratches, and dust. Soft, greyish nebula of chiaroscuro covers the central part, leaving the edges of the board brighter and cooler. Lighter spots at the bottom and the top of the cloud become discernible. Specks of reflected light move gently, gradually getting arranged in a shape of glowing, trembling strings. They move vivaciously propelled by invisible energy, to fade away a moment later, stopping half-way to non-existence. They exist there precariously for a while, struggling with the rude materiality of the white board, which they manage to seize for a while before they disappear.

¹² This is how Malevich reflected on *Black Square*, yet this description can be adopted to *Arabesque* as well.

¹³ Source of stills from *Arabesque*: Max (2013).

Fig. 6 J. Rojkowska, *Table* (2015)

When light gets stronger, it brings to view elements which have been so far hidden from sight, which – dissolved in the ocean of non-existence – have eluded perception. When light gets stronger, it gradually lets us sense something coming in a foggy cloud of indefinite shape. This “something” remains for a while between the state of being and non-being. Our brain and eyes cannot define what they see. Its existence in our consciousness hinges on a feeling, emotion, intuitive sensation of some presence. It still can step back to non-existence, leaving us with uncertainty and doubts. Light is a means of transport between worlds and dimensions. One strong flash of light brings invisible things close to the seeable world. Now we can measure their size, define the shape, tone and colour. We can give them a name.

With a one strong flash, the image, which has just entered the world of our consciousness, dissolves into a blinding glare. Losing details, it fades into non-existence. We live in a narrow reality of transitory light, which, while on its way between one invisible realm of “too little light” and another invisible realm of “too much light”, inadvertently casts to our place things and objects of vision.

Arabesque (0:30 - 0:32) and Black Square

A white rectangle with soft, rounded edges placed against a black background. There is no recognizable value except these three: light, darkness and shape. Some faint remnants of texture at the bottom of the rectangle reminds us of its material, objective origin. The shape

grows and in a few “jumps” ultimately fills the whole frame with white light. “This was no empty square [though] but rather feeling of non-objectivity. I realized that the ‘thing’ and the ‘concept’ were substituted for the feeling and understood the falsity of the world of will and idea” (Malevich, 2003, pp. 67-68).

Fig.7 G. Dulac, still from *Arabesque*, left and K. Malevich, *Black Square* (1915), right.¹⁴

Fig.8 G. Dulac, *Arabesque*, left and K. Malevich, *Eight Red Rectangles*, (1915), right.¹⁵

¹⁴ Source: America (n.d.).

¹⁵ Image source: Artdone (2013). Although here I juxtapose stills from *Arabesque* with two of Malevich's works, I conduct an in-depth analysis of *Black Square* only, bringing *Suprematist Composition with Eight Red Rectangles* exclusively as another illustration of visual links between abstract images in *Arabesque* and Suprematism. Such links of her work can be also found with other painterly works of the period, e.g. Giacomo

Many images in *Arabesque* were created using overexposure, back lighting, or reflected light. This allowed objects to move from the sphere of recognizable things to the sphere of figures. This technique employed by Dulac was noticed by Williams, who comments:

For Dulac, naturalistic techniques, which she used as a means of representing the interior or psychology of the character, gradually gave way to more specifically symbolist tendencies. To this end she employed figures and objects, as well as known cultural references (e.g., to painting and music) as a means of translating certain ideas (Williams, 2007a, p. 94).

To understand the process of abstracting taking place in *Arabesque* it is important to understand what figure is. "Figure is something in-between not being and being: a becoming that disrupts the rule of representation. . . [Figures] mark a resistance to the idea that an object is contained within a system of signification" (Miles, 2019).

The transformation from figuration to abstraction, as an artistic method, emerged before *Arabesque* and was created by those artists who developed abstraction in painting. To mention only two of Dulac's contemporaries: Piet Mondrian used the process of abstracting an object through the series of drawings and simplified it gradually to vertical and horizontal lines to express the basic order of the universe, while Malevich employed among others the technique of aerial photography.¹⁶ For neither of them, however, was abstracting a process of "translation" of ideas (as Tami Williams formulates it), but rather a way of liberating objects from the existing indexical bonds. Olga Bulgakova explains: "For Malevich the ultimate meaning of this process [evolution from figuration to abstraction] is not abandoning the imitation of nature but liberating thought from the bonds of developed categories and existing forms, including the mimetic dogma" (Bulgakova, 2002, p. 19).

This transcendence, this ability to open up for a new, broad understanding through the rejection of the mimetic dogma or system of significations attached to the figurative image is what constitutes the power of abstraction. *Black Square*, the first Suprematist painting, was created by Malevich fourteen years before *Arabesque*. Victor Stoichita in his book *A Short*

Balla's *Materiality of Light +Speed* (1915). This fact strengthens my conviction that Dulac's abstract images have much deeper, so far unexplored layers reflecting more than just feminist or psychological issues.

¹⁶ For example, "In his *Suprematist Painting: Aeroplane Flying* [1915] Malevich reduces the landscape seen below into abstract geometric forms of colour" (Cheung, 2020, p. 166).

History of the Shadow (1997) acknowledges the importance of transcending the representational image. He claims that as *Black Square* was at first a design for a stage curtain, its role was not to represent but to cover representation, or by raising it, to make representation possible. Thus, suggesting that *Black Square* was born out of the idea of a curtain, the scholar admits its anti-representational character. Similarly, as a stage curtain, *Black Square*, by covering the representation, became “an indeterminate image: the image of the representation’s infinite possibilities” (Stoichita, 1997, p. 184). Malevich said of *Black Square* that “in this terrible power lies the sum total of all the images of the universe waiting to be formed. The zenith of the mimesis kills the mimesis” (ibid. p. 189). Stoichita takes this quote and uses it to forge a connection between this description and a 19th-century caricature of a photographer staring at an overexposed, completely black photograph, thus through a technical failure achieving a “prophetic” image in the form of a photographic version of the first Suprematist painting (a black square against a white background). It is worth noticing that Dulac’s abstract images in *Arabesque* also were frequently achieved through the manipulation of light:¹⁷ too much light passing through the lens makes the illusionistic image abstract and unrecognizable. The question is, then, if these images can also be regarded as a kind of curtain: covering what was represented, they become – to paraphrase Malevich’s words – an indeterminate image of infinite possibilities. And so, instead of being narrowly understood through the perspective of Dulac’s earlier narrative works, can they – similarly to Malevich’s works – go beyond the previous indexical attachments?

Light and Matter

The difference between a still image and a filmic image relies on movement, and movement can be understood as a key element in this dialogue between Dulac’s and Malevich’s abstraction.¹⁸ In *Arabesque* this is the element, as I have already demonstrated, which holds

¹⁷ It is not the only technique used by Dulac to achieve abstract images, but the one which she applied in a large number of images in *Arabesque*, endowing them with various degrees of abstraction. In this thesis I concentrate on the use and role of light and therefore I do not mention other techniques used by her for abstracting figurative images.

¹⁸ Oksana Bulgakova mentions that “In Russia, the discourse on the representation of motion in film was influenced by Henry Bergson as he was perceived by Formalist circle . . . Bergson uses film as a metaphor of human consciousness which creates a model of the metaphysical sensation of movement that does not

the abstract image attached to its previous meaning. Let me quote Akira Mizuta Lippit (2005) on the role of movement in Dulac's films. He repeats her words as follows:

"Cinema . . . by decomposing movement, makes us see, analytically . . . the psychology of movement". (p. 62) And later he continues: "Dulac's idiom, which synthesizes metaphors of corporeality, psychology, and perception, reflects the profound dilemma that cinema poses with regard to the rhetoric of visuality. The penetrating visuality of film pierces the surface and exposes 'the psychology of movement,' the interiority of things" (ibid.).

Dulac herself mentions the analytical character of movement and connects it with the psychological dimension; Lippit simply repeated this idea. However, in view of the fact that in Dulac's times the philosophy of cinema was writing its revolutionary chapter, in which both movement and light played a key role, I think that *Arabesque's* reading would not be complete without a close look at this intellectual thread. So, I would like to propose a new perspective taking into account both the analytical character of movement and its ability to expose "the interiority of things", while still connecting the figurative image and its abstract version "born of light".

In 1896, in the wake of the birth of the cinema, Henry Bergson published *Matter and Memory*, in which he claims that there is an identity between the image and movement. The greatest revolution in the understanding of the relation between man and the universe came, however, in 1905, when Albert Einstein formulated the Theory of Special Relativity, followed by the Theory of General Relativity published in 1915.¹⁹ This idea influenced science, philosophy and art alike. In 1922 Bergson reflected on Einstein's discoveries in

correspond to reality . . . Film is not a material reproduction of movement; it transmits the idea of movement. Malevich supports this view and believes that motion is as illusory in film as in painting." In general, the attitude of Russian filmmakers differed from the French ones. According to Bulgakova (2002) "The Russian film avant-garde treated film analytically; it was concerned not with the synthesis of motion but with the realisation of the gap, an interval, a moment of stasis between the photograms" (p. 27).

The difference between the Soviet and French schools is also an outcome of the immediate cultural and political context. The dialectic which has been developed for decades around these two works (*Black Square* and *Arabesque*) is shaped by two various backgrounds. The reading of Malevich's work is strongly influenced by Russian Constructivism and materialist outlook, whereas Dulac's work – belonging to French school – is seen as "an expression of a soul" (Deleuze, 1986, p. 84).

¹⁹ In 1905, [Albert Einstein](#) published the [theory of special relativity](#), in which space and time are interwoven into a single continuum known as space-time. The most important outcome of this theory was the notion of the equivalence of mass and energy, expressed in his famous formula $E=mc^2$. It was a marked departure from Newtonian physics and laid the foundation of modern science (Redd, 2017, Fernflores, 2019).

Duration and Simultaneity.²⁰ This in turn became an inspiration for Deleuze to integrate the ideas formulated in these two books and to create the idea of the universe as meta-cinema. Paul A. Harris (2010) says that Deleuze “deduces that ‘the identity of the image and movement [in *Matter and Memory*] stems from the identity of matter and light [commented in *Duration and Simultaneity*]’ (C1, 60)”²¹ (p. 117), while Ronald Bogue (2004, p. 117) explains how Deleuze translated Bergson’s understanding of Einstein’s theory into the cinematic reflection:

*Bergson posits a primal “world of universal variation, universal undulation, universal rippling: no axes, no center, neither right nor left, neither up nor down” (IM86/5-59). This world “constitutes a sort of plane of immanence” (IM 6/5-59) in which things are indistinguishable from their movements and even from each other, a molecular, gaseous realm of fluxes. But . . . it is also a world of images-in-motion or movement-images, for “the **movement-image** and the **matter-flow** are strictly speaking the same thing” (IM87/59). The reason for this is that “the plane of immanence in its entirety is Light. The totality of movements, of actions and reactions is light which diffuses, which spreads” (IM 88/60). In this plane of immanence, then, matter=light=image=movement.*

Bearing in mind that in Dulac’s work movement is the last link between the figurative image and its abstract version, the link which she never rejected, we are coming face to face with the consistent presence of those elements which are used to build abstract shots in *Arabesque*: on the one hand, light, which abstracts the figurative image, and on the other, movement, which has the power to expose, to use her words, “the interiority of things” and frequently is the last element which allows us to identify the abstraction as linked to the recognizable entity. Deleuze’s words: “The identity of image and movement stems from the identity of matter and light” (Zepke, 2005, p. 82) signalise the ontological unity of these elements, and a shift in the meaning of the image, which this unity entails. The vision of the

²⁰ This work turned out to have a great impact in the world of culture, e.g. it inspired such writers as Marcel Proust, Thomas Mann, Virginia Woolf and T.S. Eliot in the way they broke up with the 19th-century depiction of time in literature (Harris, 2010, p. 117).

²¹ Paola Maratti (2001), on the other hand, claims that in his *Matter and Memory* (1896) Bergson sought to move beyond the dualism of classical philosophy. For him “the opposition between consciousness and the thing rests largely on the opposition between the image and movement. Images seem to be found in consciousness, whereas movements take place in space”. These ideas have been later developed by Deleuze in the context of cinema and led him to formulate the understanding of the material universe as meta-cinema (pp. 233-234).

creation of matter from light brings to mind the images from *Arabesque* made with the manipulation of light, which puts the imagery in the state of flow between figuration and abstraction:

The plane of immanence as pure light would have been an initial condition, when the rippling, undulating universe (plane of immanence) was “too hot” for bodies to emerge. After this stage, “One should conceive of a cooling down of the plane of immanence . . . It is here that the first outlines of solids or rigid and geometric bodies would be formed” (Harris, 2010, p. 119).

Dulac decomposes the visible world of matter like a physicist splitting it into particles of energy. Matter broken down into light and energy becomes, in turn, recognizable by the characteristics of its movement. In this perspective we can see that “Images, as luminous moving matter, are ‘vibrations’ (C1, 8/19), movements that express the infinite connectivity and creativity of the open and immanent plane of duration” (Zepke, 2005, p. 82).

The reading of abstract images in *Arabesque* as conveyers of social and psychological ideas, although justified to a point, seems to be too narrow if we look at them from a wider perspective – that of early 20th-century abstract art²² and science. The decomposition of the object into its formless state of light and movement in Dulac’s works can be rather seen as a response to ontological questions raised by scientific discoveries, which changed the understanding of matter and light, and through the unity these two categories turned the universe into a meta-cinema (Zepke, 2005, p. 82).

²² Futuristic images dealing with speed bear distinct resemblance to some images of the movement of machinery in *Arabesque*. In Balla’s painting *Velocity of Cars and Light* (1913) the issues of light, movement and the abstracting of an object carry physical and metaphysical consequences.

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